

STRUCTURE OF THE OBSERVED LEARNING OUTCOME (SOLO) AND LEVEL OF THINKING SKILLS IN SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the students' level of thinking skills in science using the Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome (SOLO)-based Assessment. The respondents of the study were 86 Grade 10 students of Sta. Agueda National High School. The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational method, used a research instrument adopted from Teacher Resource in Science 2022, and employed percent, mean, and Chi-square. The students' prior performance in the core subjects was also considered, showing a "Very Satisfactory" performance in English and a "Satisfactory" performance in Mathematics and Science. The research findings revealed that the majority of students exhibited a unistructural level of thinking in Learning Competency 1 (LC1), a prestructural level in LC2, and a multistructural level in LC3. Notably, relational thinking skills were found to be the least developed competency. Furthermore, the data revealed a significant relationship between students' level of thinking in science and their performance in the core subjects, including Mathematics in LC1, English in LC1 and LC2 and Science in LC1. The study also revealed that the students' level of thinking in science and their mother's educational attainment have a significant correlation.

Keywords: *SOLO-based assessment, SOLO taxonomy, higher-order thinking skills, Critical thinking, core subjects*

INTRODUCTION

Higher-order thinking skills involve more than just recalling, restating, or reciting information; they involve thinking across multiple dimensions of knowledge, including metacognitive dimensions (Astutik, Bektiarso, & Lesmono, 2019). According to Huang (2023), academic and professional successes are well-predicted by Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS). In line with this, educational institutions have the responsibility to empower society by adopting a holistic approach that integrates 21st-century skills such as Learning and Innovation skills (critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication), literacy skills (information, media, and technology), and life skills, which are necessary to prepare individuals for the changing global environment (Chiva et al., 2024). However, several studies have pointed out issues regarding the level of students' thinking abilities. To mention a few, a study by Sarwanto, Fajari, and Chumdari (2021) revealed that fifth-grade pupils have low critical thinking skills. Abdullah et al. (2019) also concluded in their study that students' ability to choose and apply the right strategies to solve the given problems is still lacking. Moreover, a study in Iraq determined that all students must strengthen their HOTS, particularly their synthesis and assessment abilities, which are needed to boost their scientific creativity. These studies all show the need to improve students' thinking skills.

Similarly, in the Philippines, research shows that Filipino students lack the skills required to become critical thinkers (Salas, 2016). In 2018, the Philippines participated in one of the International Large-Scale Assessments (ILSA), the Programme of International Student Assessment (PISA), whose results revealed that Filipino students obtained the lowest score in reading comprehension and ranked second lowest in mathematics and science literacy out of 79 involved countries (Bautista, 2023). In 2019, results from Trends in Mathematics and Scientific Study (TIMSS) also revealed that Filipino students lag behind other countries, with the Philippines ranking the lowest in Mathematics and Science (TIMSS, 2019). Furthermore, the latest PISA 2022 outcomes reveal that the Philippines ranks among the bottom in comparison to the 81 involved countries. Overall, these results attest to the fact that the Philippine education system is in crisis (Servallos, 2023).

With the results presented by international assessment bodies, Charlie Fababaer, the principal of Pasig City Science High School, which is one of the best-performing public schools in the Philippines, stated that other factors contributing to the poor PISA 2018 performance include students' unfamiliarity with the testing environment and tools that are provided, as well as their insufficient exposures to assessment questions that heavily rely on technology. (Philippines, 2022). Thus, there is a need to align classroom assessments with international standards, and classroom instruction must emphasize enhancing the higher-order thinking abilities of the students. The Department of Education (DepEd), in collaboration with the Philippine National Research Center for Teacher Quality (RCTQ), developed a resource package for teachers that integrates the principles of Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome (SOLO) taxonomy to promote effective higher-order learning among learners. The SOLO-based assessments in this

resource package are already aligned with PISA standards. Hence, it is considerably effective to be used within the learning program and during the teaching and learning process (Damopolii, 2020). Various studies utilized the SOLO taxonomy but only a few are conducted here in the Philippines since DepEd just recently introduced the tools to the teachers. Moreover, research showed that out of 500 science teachers, only 20% knew about this SOLO taxonomy, signifying that this topic is less explored (*A Teacher's Guide to SOLO Taxonomy*, 2022). Thus, the researcher considered this as the research gap.

The researchers, being science teachers, are therefore driven to explore this topic, specifically focusing on identifying the level of students' thinking skills in science using the SOLO-based assessment or SOLO taxonomy. They believed that the outcome of this research would help educators make more well-informed decisions to develop an intervention plan and enhance the delivery of instruction.

Research Questions

This study is designed to identify the students' level of thinking in science using the SOLO-based assessments.

Specifically, the study would like to answer the following questions:

1. What is the prior performance of the students in the following core subjects:
 - 1.1 Mathematics;
 - 1.2 English; and
 - 1.3 Science?

2. What is the students' level of thinking in science as measured by SOLO-based assessment in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 prestructural;
 - 2.2 unistructural;
 - 2.3 multistructural;
 - 2.4 relational; and
 - 2.5 extended abstract?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the students' performance in the core subjects and their level of thinking in science as measured by SOLO-based assessment?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the students in terms of sex and parents' educational attainment and their level of thinking in science as measured by SOLO-based assessment?

Statement of the Null Hypothesis

H_{o1}: There is no significant relationship between the prior performance of the students in the core subjects and their level of thinking in science as measured by SOLO-based assessment.

H_{o2}: There is no significant relationship between the profile of the students in terms of sex and parents' educational attainment and their level of thinking in science.

METHODOLOGY

Research design. The research utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. It is descriptive because it identified the (a) profile of the students in terms of sex and their parents' educational attainment, (b) the students' performance in the core subjects, and (c) the students' level of thinking in Science based on the SOLO-based assessment. On the other hand, it is also considered correlational because the aforementioned variables were correlated.

Research environment. The study was conducted in Barangay Sta. Agueda, one of the sixteen barangays in the Municipality of Pamplona. The barangay has two public schools, namely, Sta. Agueda Elementary School and Sta. Agueda National High School. This study, thus, considered the students from Sta. Agueda National School.

Sta. Agueda National High School belongs to Pamplona District 2 under the umbrella of the Tanjay City Division. The school is one of the biggest schools in the district distinctly featured by a wide grass field surrounded by acacia and mahogany trees, thus making it a conducive learning environment. It has a total population of 650 students for the school year 2023-2024. It has an average class size of 36. Each classroom is equipped with an LED Television for audio-visual instruction. The school also has a two-story science building where equipment is stored and laboratory activities are conducted. Moreover, it has functional computer laboratories with internet connection, desktops, and tablets essential for fostering computer literacy among students. Overall, the school meets the DepEd's guidelines for safety and usability.

Research respondents. The respondents of this research are the Grade 10 learners of Sta. Agueda National High School for the school year 2023–2024. The Grade 10 level has a total student population of 114 and consists of three sections. Only 86 students or approximately 75% of the total population were considered in the study.

Section	Population	Sample
10-Earth	35	26
10-Saturn	38	29
10-Venus	41	31
Total	114	86

Selecting the representative of the population was done using the systematic sampling technique, wherein every 2nd student in the list was selected as a respondent.

Research instruments. The study utilized two sets of questionnaires. The first questionnaire was completed by the respondents while the second one was completed by an external rater.

The first questionnaire consists of Parts I, II, and III. Part I bears the disclosure statement expressing the nature and purpose of the study. This also serves as the informed consent from the respondents. Part II is the profile of the respondents in terms of their sex, parents' educational background, and prior performance in the core subjects. The respondents' former grades were extracted from the School Form 10 (SF10) and were given to the respondents after answering the questionnaire. Part III is the assessment section, composed of three SOLO-based assessments aligned with the PISA standards and learning competencies in Grade 10 science. The SOLO-based assessments used in this study were adopted from the Teachers' Resource in Science 2022.

The second questionnaire also consists of Parts I and II. Similarly, Part I is the disclosure statement. Part II pertains to the students' level of thinking in science as measured by the SOLO-based assessment. The external rater accomplished this section by checking on the appropriate SOLO level based on the students' learning outcomes in every learning competency.

Research procedure. After the design hearing, the researcher incorporated the panel members' corrections and recommendations into the paper for refinement. With the approval of the dean of Foundation University's graduate school, a request letter to carry out the study was forwarded to the superintendent of Tanjay City's Schools Division. The approved and signed request was given to the principal of the target school. The researcher discussed with the respondents the significance and goal of the study during the questionnaire distribution. The questionnaires were retrieved as soon as the students were done answering. The completed questionnaires were forwarded to the external rater for evaluation.

The results were tallied using MS Excel and Megastat software, and then the data were analyzed and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The tools used by the researcher in analyzing the data (assuming all assumptions were met) are as follows:

Percent. This was used in presenting the students' prior performance in the core subjects and the level of students' thinking skills in science.

Mean. This was used to get the students' prior performance in core subjects.

Chi-Square Test. This was utilized to identify the degree of relationship between the students' profile (in terms of sex and parents' educational attainment) and their level of thinking in science. This test was selected since the profile is on a nominal scale.

The proficiency level or academic performance at which the students were performing was based on the following criteria (DepEd Order No. 8, s 2015).

Rating	Verbal Equivalent	Explanation
90% - 100%	Outstanding	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
80% - 84%	Satisfactory	The students at this level have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understanding but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	The students at this level struggle with his /her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Scope of the study. This research was confined to determining the students' prior performance in the core subjects, their level of thinking in science, students' profiles, and how these variables correlate with each other. The respondents of this study are the Grade 10 students at Sta. Agueda National High School situated in Sta. Agueda, Pamplona, Negros Oriental.

Limitations of the Study. This study has inherent limitations. First, the study was focused solely on Grade 10 students. It may not include a diverse range of students in terms of demographics, socioeconomic status, or cultural background, limiting the applicability of the findings to a broader context.

Second, the SOLO-based assessment is considered a new approach to assessing the learner's quality of understanding since it was recently introduced to the teachers. In addition, the teacher's presence or the testing context might have affected how students responded to the assessments. Some students might have felt pressured to perform well, impacting the authenticity of their demonstrated thinking levels. Hence, students' feeling towards the assessment is considered as a limitation.

Lastly, the study might have faced time constraint limitations since the teacher has assumed few ancillaries outside the teaching and unforeseen school activities that might disrupt classes. This limitation could affect the timeline of data collection and analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1

Prior Performance of the Students in Core Subjects (n = 86)

Rating	VD	Mathematics		English		Science	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
90 – 100	Outstanding (O)	8	9.30	20	23.26	8	9.30
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory (VS)	32	37.21	21	24.42	16	18.60
80 – 84	Satisfactory (S)	28	32.56	22	25.58	34	39.53
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	18	20.93	23	26.74	28	32.56
Total		86	100.00	86	100.00	86	100.00
Mean		83.28 (S)		84.91 (VS)		81.77 (S)	
SD		3.92		6.64		3.90	

Table 2

Students' Level of Thinking Skills in Science as Measured by SOLO-Based Assessments (n = 86)

Levels of Thinking Skills based on SOLO Taxonomy	LC1		LC2		LC3	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Prestructural	22	25.58	40	46.51	11	12.79
Unistructural	32	37.21	18	20.93	24	27.91
Multistructural	24	27.91	24	27.91	47	54.65

Relational	8	9.30	4	4.65	4	4.65
Extended Abstract	---	---	---	---	---	---
Total	86	100.00	86	100.00	86	100.00

Table 3

Performance of the Students in the Core Subjects and Their Level of Thinking Skills in Science as Measured by SOLO-Based Assessment (n = 86)

Variables	χ^2	p-value	Decision	Remark
Performance in Math and Thinking Skills in...				
LC1	16.762	0.002	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Thinking Skills	Math Performance		
	Prestructural:	80.41%		
	Unistructural:	84.19%		
	Multistructural/Relational:	84.34%		
LC2	4.801	0.308	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
LC3	4.793	0.309	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Performance in English and Thinking Skills in...				
LC1	25.188	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Thinking Skills	English Performance		
	Prestructural:	79.27%		
	Unistructural:	86.44%		
	Multistructural/Relational:	87.25%		
LC2	17.431	0.008	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Thinking Skills	English Performance		
	Prestructural:	82.98%		
	Unistructural:	88.50%		
	Multistructural/Relational:	85.36%		
LC3	8.915	0.178	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Performance in Science and Thinking Skills in...				
LC1	21.518	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
	Thinking Skills	Science Performance		
	Prestructural:	78.59%		
	Unistructural:	83.25%		
	Multistructural/Relational:	82.47%		
LC2	7.048	0.133	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
LC3	1.903	0.754	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 4

Relationship between the Profile of the Students in Terms of Sex and Parents' Educational Attainment and Their Level of Thinking Skills in Science (n = 86)

Variables	χ^2	p-value	Decision	Remark
Sex and Thinking Skills in...				
LC1	1.503	0.682	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
LC2	4.225	0.238	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
LC3	1.489	0.685	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Father Educational Attainment and Thinking Skills in...				
LC1	8.132	0.087	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
LC2	5.250	0.263	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
LC3	6.404	0.171	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Mother Educational Attainment and Thinking Skills in...				
LC1	9.281	0.054	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
LC2	5.451	0.244	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
LC3	10.472	0.033	Reject H_{02}	Significant
	Educational Attainment		Thinking	
	College Level/Graduate:	2.47		
	High School Level/Graduate:	2.55		
	Elementary Level/Graduate:	2.34		

Level of significance = 0.05

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the data on students' prior performance in the core subjects, which include Mathematics, English, and Science. As shown in the results, the grade 9 students' prior academic performance in Mathematics and Science is "Satisfactory" with mean ratings of 83.28 and 81.77, respectively. Meanwhile, the respondents showed "Very Satisfactory" performance in English as reflected in its mean rating of 84.91. These results contradict the research findings of Santisteban and Futralan (2024), wherein students exhibited an "Outstanding" performance in English and "Very Satisfactory" performance in Mathematics and Science. The results implied that the grade 9 students at this level have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understanding and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks in English, while little assistance from a "More Knowledgeable Others" is needed in Mathematics and Science (DepEd Order No.8, s. 2015). The findings of the study contradict the claims of Capuno et al. (2019) and the results of PISA in 2018, ILSA, and TIMSS 2019, which revealed that most Filipino students considered Mathematics and Science as difficult subjects, thus leading to their unsatisfactory performance in the said subject areas. Furthermore, the result is also in disagreement with the national test scores in the 2019 National

Achievement Test (NAT) in Mathematics where both Grade 6 and Grade 10 students fall under the “low mastery” level (Tagupa, 2019).

Table 2 presents the data on the students' level of thinking skills in science as measured by SOLO-based assessments. The level of thinking skills utilized in the study is based on the SOLO taxonomy by Biggs and Collis (1982). In this study, there are three learning competencies (LC) that were measured, namely: (1) describe the feedback mechanisms involved in regulating processes in the female reproductive system (e.g., menstrual cycle); (2) describe how the nervous system coordinates and regulates these feedback mechanisms to maintain homeostasis; and (3) explain how protein is made using information from DNA.

In LC1, the majority of students demonstrate unistructural thinking skills, representing 37.21% of the cohort, followed by those in the multistructural level at 27.91%, and prestructural level at 25.58%. Relational thinking skills are least represented at 9.30%. In LC2, the data reveal that the highest percentage of students (46.51%), exhibit prestructural thinking, followed by 27.91% in the multistructural level and 20.93% in the unistructural level. Relational thinking remains the least common at 4.65%. Moving to LC3, the analysis indicates that the majority of students (54.65%), demonstrate multistructural thinking skills, followed by 27.91% in the unistructural level and 12.79% in the prestructural level. Relational thinking skills remain at the lowest percentage, with 4.65%.

Generally, the data suggest variations in students' levels of thinking skills across the three competencies. The majority of students fall under the multistructural level in LC3, indicating a higher level of thinking complexity. Moreover, prestructural thinking dominates LC2 and unistructural thinking prevails in LC1, while relational thinking remains consistently low across all competencies, suggesting a need for further development in critical thinking skills at this level.

A similar finding was also manifested in the study of Tian et al. (2020) on evaluating students' computation skills in learning the amount of substance which revealed that the majority of students fall under the multistructural level, demonstrating proficiency in solving relatively straightforward problems and applying basic formulas. Moreover, only a small fraction of students reached the advanced relational level, showcasing their ability to apply chemical concepts and methodologies to solve complex problems (Tian et al., 2020).

Further, a similar study that dealt with the effectiveness of Inquiry-based Learning (IBL) to train students' thinking skills based on SOLO taxonomy concluded that students' thinking skills are spread all over the level of SOLO taxonomy, from pre-structural to the extended abstract but most of the students' thinking skills are on multi-structural level (Damopolii et al., 2020).

The presented research findings imply that the educational process should emphasize developing higher cognitive skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking,

and creative thinking for the students to reach the “Extended Abstract” level of SOLO. Furthermore, empowering teachers to employ effective strategies to elicit advanced cognitive abilities through implementing assessments with a high level of complexity is recommended to further develop the students’ 21st-century skills.

Table 3, unveils the data in identifying the relationship between the performance of the students in core subjects and their level of thinking skills in science as measured by SOLO-Based assessment. Considering the performance in Mathematics and thinking skills of the students, the data exposed that a significant relationship exists only in LC1 with p-value (0.002), which is less than the level of significance (0.05). The data further reveal that as the Math performance of the students increases, their level of thinking skills also increases. This result is an affirmation of the findings of Tanujaya, Mumu and Margono (2017) which show a significant relationship between HOTS and Mathematics performance. Similarly, the research findings of Santisteban and Futralan (2024) exhibited a significant correlation between Mathematics performance and students’ thinking skills. Furthermore, the study of Celik and Ozdemir (2020) also pointed out that mathematical thinking skills and problem-solving skills are predictors of critical thinking dispositions.

Concerning students’ performance in English and thinking skills, the data reflect that a significant relationship exists between the variables in LC1 ($p = <.001$) and LC2 ($p = < 0.008$). Moreover, the data show, based on the ratings of the students, that those who have better performance in English tend to have higher thinking skills.

Through language learning, learners develop functional and critical literacy skills (K to 12 English Curriculum Guide, 2016). The result of this study is supported by the study of Kulamikhina et al. (2018), which concluded that literature reading has improved the overall critical thinking skills of the learners who have scored low in a pretest. Additionally, a research study on the impact of creative writing on learners’ thinking skills has shown significant improvement in critical thinking (Tung & Chang, 2009; Marcos et al., 2020). Furthermore, the study of Sholikhah et al. (2021) affirmed that *there was a high positive significant linear correlation between HOTS and English achievement*. Hence, achieving proficiency in English can help develop students’ higher-order level of thinking skills. On the contrary, research shows that there is no significant relationship between English performance and students’ thinking skills (Santisteban & Futralan, 2024).

In the area of performance in science and thinking skills, the data reveal that a significant relationship exists between the variables only in LC1 ($p = <.001$). As indicated, students who have unistructural, multistructural, and relational levels of thinking skills have higher performance than those students who are at the prestructural level. Based on the description of SOLO levels by Biggs and Collis (1982), the research finding indicates that those students who acquired basic knowledge involving knowing and understanding one or more relevant concepts and could make meaningful connections of the concepts would achieve better performance in science. This is supported by Binder et al. (2019), who professed that knowledge about principles and concepts was a significant predictor of better performance in biology and knowledge about concepts and principles as well as the ability to apply knowledge to problems was related to academic

achievement in physics. Moreover, this result is affirmed by Santisteban and Futralan (2024), who found that students' ability to apply critical thinking to real-life situations is strongly correlated with their performance in science.

Based on the presented research findings, it can be deduced that strengthening proficiency in Mathematics, English, and foundational Science knowledge can contribute to the development of higher-order thinking skills among students. Furthermore, it can be implied that educators should consider integrating interdisciplinary approaches and fostering a supportive learning environment to facilitate the cultivation of critical thinking abilities across subjects.

Table 4 indicates the relationship between the profile of the students and their level of thinking skills in science. The data divulge that the students' sex is not related to their level of thinking skills in LC1, LC2, and LC3 (all p-values $> \alpha = 0.05$). This means that their sex cannot account for how they think critically in science-related problems.

The result affirms the research findings of Sagala (2019) positing that there is no interaction between learning and gender towards concepts understanding in physics. In other words, higher-order thinking skills cannot be solely attributed to sex. The same finding is observed by Nguyen et al. (2023), who declared that developing HOTS, which involves thinking process of applying, analyzing, and evaluating, is not at all times influenced by sex but it is also affected by several factors such as teachers' attitude, teachers' skills in developing critical thinking, interest of students' parents, and critical thinking activities. On the contrary, the research findings of Nasution, Muhdhar, and Sari (2023) revealed that sex has a significant relationship with students' creative thinking skills in biology.

The table also points out that the father's educational attainment is not significantly associated (all p-values $> \alpha = 0.05$) with how the students use their thinking skills in science. This finding means that regardless of the educational qualifications of the father, the student's thinking skills do not vary. Meanwhile, the data present that the mother's educational attainment is significantly associated ($p = 0.033 < \alpha = 0.05$) with the student's level of thinking skills in LC3. This connotes that students whose mothers have at least reached high school level or graduated in high school possess higher levels of thinking skills than those students with mothers who have reached the elementary level or are elementary graduates only.

This finding is supported by research, indicating that the impact of parental educational attainment differs for fathers and mothers, with only the educational level of the mother influencing a child's academic performance (Crede et al., 2015; Hu et al., 2024).

Conclusions

Developing advanced cognitive abilities is crucial and imperative for improving educational achievements. The study demonstrates the prevalence of basic thinking skills in science, indicating a need for improvement towards higher levels of complexity such as relational and extended abstract levels. Improving proficiency in Mathematics and English is essential for nurturing students' cognitive capabilities in science, serving as the bedrock for comprehending scientific principles and articulating scientific concepts. The SOLO-based assessment served as a helpful instrument for fostering HOTS among students. Educators equipped with effective teaching strategies are pivotal in guiding students towards higher-order thinking abilities, aligning with the evolving needs of 21st-century learners. Additionally, parental support is integral to this transformative journey in enhancing cognitive skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended to school administrators, teachers, parents and future researchers:

School Administrators

1. Provide technical assistance to teachers in enhancing students' higher cognitive skills, especially in the core learning areas.
2. Ensure consistent classroom observations as outlined in the Manual for Instructional Supervision (MIS) to monitor teaching practices and student progress effectively with emphasis on developing a higher level of cognition.

Teachers

3. Incorporate SOLO-based assessment methods into teaching practices to better evaluate and enhance students' thinking skills.
4. Develop students' mathematical and English skills to better improve students' abilities in reading and comprehension, logical, and mathematical skills, which are imperative in science.
5. Explore and implement engaging teaching techniques and strategies that would focus on promoting and developing higher-order thinking skills like analysis, evaluation, and creation to enrich students' learning experiences.

Parents

6. Closely monitor and support their children's academic progress to provide additional encouragement and guidance outside of the classroom.

Future Researchers

7. Conduct an in-depth exploration (qualitative study) of the teaching practices focusing on how teachers promote HOTS in the classroom, specifically on the methods of lesson delivery and assessment (formative and summative).

8. Focus future study on the innovation of learning models or interactive simulations on least learned learning competencies in science that would help learners progress to the higher complexity of cognition (relational and extended abstract levels) and conduct a comparative study of the learning models or interactive simulations. Explore other forms of assessment such as integrative assessment involving the core subjects since they are found to be significant in developing HOTS of the learners.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers, being cautious with all the prerequisites of ethical considerations, first secured ethical approval from the Ethical Committee of the University Research Office. The appropriate practices and set of guidelines were all observed by the researcher during the entire duration of the study. All the data gathered are held with utmost confidentiality and the anonymity and identity of the respondents were preserved by not revealing their names in the data collection, analysis and reporting of findings of the study.

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